

the *product* was obtained in prismatic needles (0.4 g.), m.p. 118°. (Found: C, 83.4; H, 5.9. $C_{21}H_{13}O_2$ requires C, 83.4; H, 5.9%). On keeping in alcoholic solution or even in the solid state, the melting point slowly rose to that of the stable epimeride, m.p. 153° (*vide infra*). The benzoyl derivative, prepared in pyridine solution, was obtained as hard prisms, m.p. 138.5°, identical with benzoyl derivative of its epimeride. (Found: C, 82.6; H, 5.4. Calc. for $C_{28}H_{22}O_3$: C, 82.7; H, 5.4%). On hydrolysis with alkali the stable epimer, mentioned above, was obtained, m.p. 153°, after several crystallisations.

The compound (B) on similar hydrogenation quickly absorbed one mole of hydrogen and the product crystallised from alcohol in colorless leaflets, m.p. 153°; the mixed m.p. with the unstable isomer (m.p. 118°) was 135°, clearing at 138° and the mixed m.p. with the catalytic hydrogenation product (m.p. 143-45°) (Chatterjea, *loc. cit.*) was 149°, clearing at 152°. (Found: C, 83.5; H, 6.0. Calc. for $C_{21}H_{13}O_2$: C, 83.4; H, 5.9%).

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PHENOLIC OXIDATION. PART III. STRUCTURE OF ABEL'S ABNORMAL OXIME

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Dischendorfer's supposed identification of an abnormal oxime, isolated by Abel from dehydro-*bis*(2-hydroxy-1-naphthyl)-methane with 3:4-6:7-dibenzoacridone, has now been disproved by a direct synthesis of the latter. Alternative structures for the 'oxime' have been discussed.

In previous papers evidence was put forward and discussed in support of the structure (I) for dehydro-*bis*(2-hydroxy-1-naphthyl)-methane (Chatterjea, this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 275; 1958, 35, 37; cf. Pummerer and Cherbuliez, *Ber.*, 1914, 47, 3477; Shearing and Similes, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1931). A second structure (II, R=H), advanced originally by Kohn and Ostersetzer (*Monatsh.*, 1918, 39, 299), was specially supported by Dischendorfer (*Ber.*, 1926, 59, 774) who supposed that an 'abnormal oxime' $C_{21}H_{13}NO$ (oxime

minus one mol. of water), normally isolated from (I) by Abel (*Ber.*, 1892, 25, 3477), was the dibenzoacridone (III) and explained its formation by supposing that the normal oxime derived from (II: R=H) rearranged, the oxygen migrating from nitrogen to the central carbon atom, furnishing (IV) as an "intermediate" which passed into (III) with the elimination of a molecule of water. The yellow colour of the 'abnormal oxime', its high melting point, its solubility in alcoholic alkali and the isolation di- β -naphthylamine from it by zinc dust distillation led Dischendorfer to suppose its identity with (III); his conception gained support from his observation that (II: R=Ph) in which hydrogen atom was not attached to the central carbon atom did afford a normal oxime.

It may, however, be pointed out that the internal oxidation-reduction, as postulated by Dischendorfer, is without any known analogy. Further, the compound (II: R=Ph) cannot yield any acridone, if at all, for $\equiv\text{C}\cdot\text{Ph}$ part of the molecule will have to be changed into $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ and the severity of zinc dust distillation also makes its precise significance in respect of the compound's structure rather doubtful. A direct synthesis of (III) was therefore felt very desirable.

2-Chloro-1-naphthoic acid was condensed with β -naphthylamine in the presence of copper in amyl alcohol, affording the intermediate (V). The yield was only 1-2%; efforts to raise it under various conditions were unsuccessful on account of the tendency of formation of various byproducts and, in agreement, Cymerman-Craig and Loder (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 4309) reported that the Ullmann condensation of 1-bromo-2-naphthoic acid with α -naphthylamine yielded only 2-naphthoic acid. Further work with the acid (V) was not possible. Finally, methyl 2-hydroxynaphthalene-1-carboxylate (new preparation) was condensed with *N*- β -naphthylbenzimidoyl chloride, giving rise to

to the ether (VI), which smoothly underwent the Chapman rearrangement (*ibid.*, 1927, 1743; Jamison and Turner, *ibid.*, 1937, 1954; Cymerman-Craig and Loder, *loc. cit.*), affording the acridone (III) in good yield. The product was clearly *different* from Abel's oxime.

The oxime' has now been briefly examined. This compound is very stable and can be sublimed. It is non-basic, contains no active hydrogen and is reduced by zinc-acetic acid or by catalytic hydrogenation (Adams' catalyst) or lithium aluminium hydride to a colorless dihydro derivative. The latter contains an active hydrogen but could not be acylated. The presence of quinonoid nucleus is strongly suggestive and the expressions (VII) or (VIIa) are provisionally advanced for this compound (cf. Kohn *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) Of these, (VII) is preferred on chemical grounds although the infra-red analysis favours the expression (VIIa). The I. R. spectra of the oxime and its dihydro derivative had many features in common. The relevant bands of the former are at $6.02 \mu\text{M}$ (α - β -unsaturated ketone), $6.17 \mu\text{M}$ ($=\text{C}=\text{N}-$) and that of the reduced product at $5.98 \mu\text{S}$ (α - β -unsaturated ketone), $6.33 \mu\text{S}$ (NH deformation) and an absence of hydroxyl band. The oxime also formed an ether-soluble complex with methylmagnesium iodide and could be recovered *unchanged* from it. This is indicative of an initial complex formation at a tertiary nitrogen atom and also disposes of the possibility of the expression (VIIa) for the compound.

The 3"-bromo derivative of (I) (Shearing and Smiles, *loc. cit.*) did not form any oxime; on oximation it afforded either amorphous or unchanged compound.

During this work several *o*-arylxanthenes were prepared by the action of aromatic aldehydes on 2-naphthol.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Chloro-1-naphthoic Acid (cf. Rabe, *Ber.*, 1889, 22, 394).—A mixture of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthoic acid (5.0 g.) and PCl_5 (12.0 g.) was heated in a sealed tube at 190° for 8 hours. The resulting liquid mass was allowed to evaporate and the oily residue treated with water and left overnight. The dirty solid that separated was extracted with sodium carbonate and acidified to afford the chloro-acid which crystallised from water (charcoal) in colorless prismatic needles, m.p. $155-57^\circ$ (lit. m.p. $152-53^\circ$); yield 1.2 g.

Condensation of 2-Chloro-1-naphthoic Acid with β -Naphthylamine.—A mixture of the above chloro-acid (0.6 g.), β -naphthylamine (0.42 g.), dry potassium carbonate (0.5 g.), freshly precipitated copper (15 mg.) and amyl alcohol (3 c.c.) was refluxed in an oil-bath for 4 hours. The solution soon turned purple and the reaction mixture was poured into water; amyl alcohol and β -naphthylamine were removed by steam-distillation. The aqueous solution was filtered from the blue residue and acidified, when a yellow gummy precipitate was obtained. The acid (V) crystallised from alcohol in pale yellowish prisms, m.p. 153° (evolution of gas); the melt solidified and remelted at $169-70^\circ$ (corresponding to the m.p. of di- β -naphthylamine). (Found: N, 4.0. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires N, 4.4%). The melt was insoluble in alkali.

Methyl 2-hydroxynaphthalene-1-carboxylate was prepared in an excellent yield and purity by the action of one molecular proportion of diazomethane on an ethereal solution of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthoic acid. On working up in the usual manner, the ester was obtained as colorless needles, m.p. 8° (Schmitt and Burkard, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 2702, report m.p. 76°).

1-Methoxycarbonyl-2-naphthyl-N- β -naphthylbenzimidate (VI) was prepared from the foregoing ester and *N- β -naphthylbenzimidoyl chloride* by closely following the recipe of Cymerman-Craig and Loder (*loc. cit.*). The crude gummy product crystallised from methanol, furnishing the ether in colorless prisms, m.p. 108° . (Found: N, 3.1. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_3\text{N}$ requires N, 3.2%).

3:4-6:7-Dibenzoacridone (III).—The foregoing ether (0.15 g.) was heated in a metal bath at 280° when the formation of methyl benzoate was noted. The temperature was slowly raised to 320° during 15 minutes. The cooled mass was extracted with hot acetic acid when straw-yellow plates of the *dibenzoacridone* separated (0.08 g.), m.p. $308-209^\circ$; mixed m.p. with Abel's oxime (m.p. 360°) was $285-95^\circ$. (Found: C, 85.2; H, 4.5; N, 4.7. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{13}\text{ON}$ requires C, 85.4; H, 4.4; N, 4.7%). The compound dissolved in sulphuric acid with a light yellow solution, exhibiting a strong violet fluorescence.

Abel's Oxime.—This was prepared according to Dischendorfer (*loc. cit.*). On treating this compound with methylmagnesium iodide (excess), no gas was evolved; the material passed into an orange solution and gradually an orange complex separated. The orange solution was filtered under nitrogen, acidified, ether removed and the resulting yellow compound was identified as the original material. On fusion with potassium hydroxide, traces of a primary amine (diazo coupling test) along with unchanged material were obtained. *I. R. spectrum*: Bands at 6.02 M, 6.17 M, 7.32 M, 7.64 M, 7.91 M, 8.25 M, 9.32 M, 10.38 M, 10.74 M, 11.90 M, 12.31 M, 12.48 μ .

Reduction of the 'Oxime'.—(a). A suspension of the compound (1.5 g.) in boiling acetic acid (50 c.c.) was treated with zinc dust (5 g.) till the yellow particles disappeared ($\frac{1}{2}$ hour); the mixture was filtered and added to water. The precipitated mass crystallised from acetic acid in colorless plates (0.6 g.), m.p. 322-24° (decomp). (Found: C, 84.5; H, 5.2. $C_{21}H_{13}ON$ requires C, 84.8; H, 5.0%). The compound dissolved in H_2SO_4 with an orange colour, turning yellow and finally greenish. The compound liberated methane with methylmagnesium iodide and could be recovered back from the resulting ethereal solution. On attempted acetylation with acetic anhydride—pyridine, the original material was obtained. Attempts to oxidise the compound to the 'oxime' with ferric chloride were unsuccessful. *I. R. spectrum*: Bands at 5.98 S, 6.33 S, 7.05 S, 7.32 S, 9.32 M, 10.35 M, 10.69 M, 11.05 M, 11.59 M and 12.48 μ .

(b). A suspension of the 'oxime' (0.5 g.) in acetic acid (30 c.c.) was hydrogenated at the room temperature and atmospheric pressure with Adams' catalyst (0.1 g.) for 24 hours. A mixture of the unchanged compound and the dihydro derivative (m.p. 322-24°, yield 30%) was obtained and separated by crystallisation from acetic acid.

(c). On treating an ethereal suspension of the compound (0.5 g.) with lithium aluminium hydride (0.3 g.), the crystals turned orange but gradually went into solution (12 hours) at the room temperature. On working up, a small quantity (ca. 0.15 g.) of the dihydro compound, m.p. 322-23°, was obtained.

The reduction could not be brought about by sodium borohydride in methanol.

9-Aryldibenzoxanthenes.—The following xanthenes were prepared by adding HCl (conc.) to a mixture of β -naphthol (2 M) and appropriate aromatic aldehyde in acetic acid at the room temperature.

1:2-7:8-*Dibenzo-9-p-toluyloxanthene* crystallised from acetic acid in colorless glistening plates, m.p. 231°. (Found: C, 90.6; H, 5.5. $C_{28}H_{20}O$ requires C, 90.4; H, 5.4%).

1:2-7:8-*Dibenzo-9-p-anisylloxanthene* crystallised from butanol in colorless shining leaflets, m.p. 208°. (Found: C, 86.0; H, 5.2. $C_{28}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 86.6; H, 5.1%).

1:2-7:8-*Dibenzo-9-p-nitrophenylloxanthene* crystallised from butanol in yellowish plates, m.p. 290°. (Found: C, 80.3; H, 4.2. $C_{27}H_{17}O_2N$ requires C, 80.4; H, 4.1%).

1:2-7:8-Dibenzo-9- α -naphthylxanthene crystallised from a large volume of acetic acid in thick plates, m.p. 240°. (Found: C, 90.7; H, 5.2. $C_{31}H_{20}O$ requires C, 91.2; H, 4.9%).

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